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**HEDGING FOREIGN EXCHANGE EXPOSURE FOR FOREIGN
CURRENCY RISK
CASE STUDY OF FIVE TEA EXPORTERS COMPANIES IN
RWANDA**

By

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Master's Degree in Finance.**

KIGALI INDEPENDENT UNIVERSITY (ULK)

September, 2022

DECLARATION

This is my unique work, and I, **MUHAWENIMANA Joselyne**, proclaim it to be such. To the best of my knowledge, it has never been submitted for any other or similar prize at any other higher educational institution. As a result, I certify that this work is entirely my own and is based on research conducted as part of the requirements for the award of a Master of Business Administration degree.

Signature

Date:

CERTIFICATION

I certify that the present research project on hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk with a case study of five tea exporters companies in Rwanda was done and presented by **MUHAWENIMANA Joselyne** under my supervision.

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. MBONIGABA Celestin

Signature

DEDICATION

To my beloved husband

To my lovely friends

To my relatives,

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my deepest thanks to all those who helped and encouraged me to pursue this masters' studies. First of all I would like to thank my Lord Jesus who gave me this opportunity to study my master's program at Kigali Independent University (ULK).

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LIST OF SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

BNR	: National Bank of Rwanda
Dr.	: Doctor
GDP	: Gross Domestic Product
MINAGRI	: Ministry of Agriculture and Animal Resources
MINICOM	: Ministry of Trade and Industry
NAEB	: National Agricultural Export Development Board
FX	: Foreign Exchange
NISR	: National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda
r	: Coefficient of Correlation
SPSS	: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
UK	: United Kingdom
ULK	: Independent University of Kigali
UNDAP	: United Nations Development Assistance Plan
US\$	: United States Dollars

ABSTRACT

The title of this work is “**Hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk with a case study of five tea exporters companies in Rwanda**”. The general objective of the study was to examine the influence of Hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk control; while the specific objectives were the followings: (1) exploring the role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters, (2) analyzing the impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters and (3) determining the effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. A descriptive and correlational research design has been adopted. Questionnaires, interview and documentation have been used as techniques of collecting data whereby the 50 respondents from the five selected tea exporters companies in Rwanda have been given questionnaires, the director managers the five selected tea exporters companies have been interviewed. The study hypotheses have been accepted due to the values of coefficient of correlation (r), value of probability (P-Value) and linear plot information. The findings indicated that the all independent variables (Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure together cause variation in dependent variable at 97.8% as it was indicated by the values of R-Squared. Through ANOVA method, the study revealed clearly that Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure significantly influences foreign currency risks control in Tea Exporters Companies in Rwanda. The study hypotheses verification implied the achievement of the study objectives. The study recommended the tea exporters Companies in Rwanda to compare the cash flows that could be expected from each hedging technique before determining which technique to apply, to avoid inaccurate earnings forecasts, inadequate forward contracts for some currencies and avoid accounting distractions and to promote diversification of production facilities, try to balance insurance against profit as some hedging strategies reduce profits. After revealing this positive influence of hedging foreign currency exposure in foreign currency risks control, we suggested other researchers to conduct a study on the factors that hinder foreign currency exposure.

Key words: Hedging, foreign exchange, exposure and currency risk

CHAPTER 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

Hedging currency risk reduces the volatility of equity investments and aims to provide risk control by allowing investors to separate currency risk from their equity asset allocations. A forex hedge is a transaction implemented to protect an existing or anticipated position from an unwanted move in exchange rates. Forex hedges are used by a broad range of market participants, including investors, traders and businesses. The main goal of this thesis is to examine hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk with a case study of tea exporters in Rwanda.

1.2. Background of the study

Worldwide, Exchange rate variations over time are a potential source of risk to cross-border financial obligations and trade-related transactions. Concern about the potentially disruptive financial and real consequences of such variations are reflected in the policy of some countries to explicitly limit the nominal variability of their currency vis-à-vis that of others. While this ‘fear of floating’ is the result of a complicated array of competing considerations, it nonetheless illustrates that limiting exchange rate variability ranks well ahead of other policy objectives in some countries (Hausmann, Panizza and Stein (2002)).

In Africa, by enabling investors to keep currency risk separate from their allocations for equity assets, currency risk hedging lowers the volatility of equity investments and tries to provide risk control. A forex hedge is a transaction carried out to guard against an unfavorable change in currency rates for an expected or existing position. Forex hedges are used by a broad range of market participants, including investors, traders and businesses (Mbabazi et al, 2014).

The experience with the exchange rates has in many ways differed from what was anticipated in 1973 when the major industrialized countries abandoned the effort to keep the values of their currencies fixed. There is a wide spread feeling that exchange rates have turned out to be more volatile than they were expected to be, than they should be and perhaps than they need to be (Frankel, 1995). Exchange rate volatility creates special problem for international business activity (exporting and importing) because it creates a special kind of risk (foreign exchange risk). When business deals are arranged for the future, they are complicated by the increased risk of exchange rate changes (Evans Taylor and Holzman, 1985).

In Rwanda, the agriculture sector remains the engine of the Rwandan economy (UNDAP, 2013). It provided more than 30% of the GDP for the last decade and is still offering employment opportunities to 68% of the Rwandan population with 76% living in rural areas (NISR, 2015). It is dominated by small-scale subsistence farming under traditional agricultural practices and rain-fed agriculture (Broka et al., 2016). Tea and Coffee are major agricultural export crops and origin of foreign currencies since 1930 (NAEB, 2011).

Following the genocide of 1994, tea industry averagely experiences good returns resulting from using the best clones grown and efficient and diligent plucking allowing to produce the brightest, briskest and most aromatic tea in the world (MINAGRI, 2013). The volume of tea production and exports have almost doubled in Rwanda in the recent decade, which helped to triple the earnings from tea exports, bringing it to above US\$60 million in 2016 (World Bank, 2017).

To boost exports, Rwanda has amongst others set up the exchange rate policy whose core objective is to preserve the external value of the national currency and also to ensure the effective operation of the foreign exchange market (Mukunzi, 2004). Rwanda introduced a flexible exchange rate regime in 1995 (BNR, 2015) with the goal to stabilize the exchange rate and prices to enhance the

economic growth as well as to link that national foreign exchange market to the world market (Mukunzi, 2004).

According to Mckenzie (1999), there exists a long-run relationship between the volume of a countries exports and the level of economic activity of the importing country, the real exchange rate as well as the measure of exchange rate risk. The end results of exchange rate volatility on trade have long been at the center of the discussions on the optimality of different exchange-rate regimes (Buguk et al., 2003). The exchange rate volatility impacts on exports by creating gains or losses to farmers and exporters. The total value of export earnings depends not only on the volumes of exports traded abroad but also on the worth paid for them (Faridi, 2012). This study investigated hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk with a case study of tea exporters in Rwanda.

1.3. Problem statement

Exchange rate volatility has complicated the exporting business in Rwanda. Exporting firms adopt Foreign Exchange Risk Management as solution to these volatile exchange rates because of their impact on firm's financial performance. To most firms the objective of foreign exchange risk management is to protect funds, which a company possesses or can expect in the near future. Firms hedging foreign exchange exposure is carried out purposively to minimize quarter-to-quarter or year-to-year earnings fluctuations stemming from currency movements (MINICOM, 2019).

In Rwanda, Tea Exporting firms identified that foreign exchange risk as a problem to their businesses. This is due to some losses that tea exporters incur due to currency fluctuations (NAEB, 2019). This problem pushed the researcher to investigate the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk.

There is a knowledge gap as some researches were conducted on the effect of Exchange Rate Fluctuation on Rwandan Tea Price and Exports (Kabayiza et al., 2019), but all these previous studies didn't point out the foreign currency hedging approaches adopted by the tea exporters in order to manage this problem of foreign exchange exposure. In this way, this study established the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk control with a case study of tea exporters in Rwanda.

1.4. Objectives of the study

This study had the general objective and specific objectives

1.4.1. General objective of the study

The general objective of the study was to examine the role of hedging foreign exchange exposure in minimizing the foreign currency risk.

1.4.2. Specific objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study were be the followings;

1. To explore the role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda
2. To analyze the impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda
3. To find out the effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda

1.5. Research questions

The study was be guided by the following questions;

1. How hedging Transaction exposure affects foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

2. How Hedging Translation exposure influence foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

3. How hedging Operating exposure works on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

1.6. Hypotheses of the study

The hypotheses of the study were the followings;

1. Hedging Transaction exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

2. Hedging Translation exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

3. Hedging Operating exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda?

1.7. Scope of the study

This study was limited in terms of domain, space and in time

1.7.1. Scope in domain

In terms of domain, this research dealt with the domain of economics, especially on the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk.

1.7.2. Scope in space

In terms of space, this research was conducted in Rwanda.

1.7.3. Scope in time

In terms of time, this research was conducted in limited time from 2015 to 2021

1.8. Significance of the study

Conducting this study, the research will benefit the various categories of people such as: The researcher, the government of Rwanda and the other researchers.

1.8.1. To the researcher

Conducting this study, the researcher gained more knowledge and skills and improve the acquired ones in economics issues especially those concerning hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk. The researcher will be also awarded with a Master's degree in sciences in economics to be recognized into academic community.

1.8.2. To the government

This research will assist the government of Rwanda especially the planners and decision makers in the domain of international trade, agriculture board and exchange rate control.

1.8.3. To the other researchers

This research will be helpful to other researchers because it motivates to conduct research on the related topics. The research is also helping other students who do their researches in other domains because this work aims to serve as a secondary data for the institution's library.

1.9. Thesis structure

This thesis was organized into five chapters, for this case, the first chapter covers the introductory part of the study which includes introduction, background of the study, statement of the problem, research objectives, research questions, the significance of the study and origination of the study.

Second chapter provides the related literature review that involves conceptual review, theoretical review, empirical review, conceptual framework and research gap.

Chapter three examined the methodology adopted for the study in terms of research design, data collection techniques and tools, methods of data collection, data and econometrics methodology, limitations and ethical considerations.

Chapter four presents the data analysis and interpretation of results. In this chapter, research results were discussed so that meaningful conclusion could be drawn. In the same chapter formulated hypotheses were verified.

Chapter five deals with the summary of the study, conclusion, recommendations and suggestions for further research.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

This chapter involves the conceptual review, theoretical review, empirical review, research gap and conceptual framework.

2.2. Conceptual review

This part provides the meaning of the study key concepts which are hedging foreign exchange exposure and foreign currency risk.

2.2.1. Hedging foreign exchange exposure

Hedging is a financial strategy implemented by investors to protect their investment portfolios from the risk of adverse price movements that could lead to the loss of value. Hedging is an important task for firms that are exposed to foreign-exchange-rate risk and want to minimise the uncertainty associated with unexpected changes in the exchange rate. Corporate managers are becoming aware of the need to manage foreign-exchange risk from a strategic point of view, and to take into account the movement of the exchange rate and its effect on future cash flows in the long run (Dhani and Groves, 2001).

Levi (2005) defines exposure as 'the sensitivity of changes in the real domestic-currency value of assets or liabilities to changes in exchange rates in other words, it is the amount at risk'. Jorion (1990) defines exchange-rate exposure as the sensitivity of the value of the firm to the randomness of the exchange rate, which is measured by the slope of the regression coefficient between changes in the value of the firm and changes in the exchange rate. Moosa (2010) defines foreign-exchange exposure as 'a measure of the sensitivity of what is at risk to the source of risk'. In other words,

exposure measures the sensitivity of the domestic-currency value of foreign-currency items, such as assets, liabilities, and cash flows, to the change in the exchange rate. The source of risk in the foreign exchange is the change in the exchange rate.

Foreign-exchange-rate exposure can be classified into three kinds: economic (operating) exposure; transaction exposure; and translation exposure. In their study of the British Times 1000 Corporations, Belk and Edelshain (1997) show that the three exposures are linked to each other. They argue that economic exposure in the future will be converted into transaction exposure, and that the choice of the currency by a firm for its future cash flows will consequently affect its revenues and expenses reported in the income statement (translation exposure). Therefore, anything that affects economic exposure will definitely affect the other two exposures. Marshall (2000) points out that these exposures are interrelated and not separate, as a firm might be affected by more than one type.

2.2.2. Foreign currency risk

Adler and Dumas (1984) define foreign-exchange risk as the probability of a change in a foreign currency on a specific future date. In other words, it is related to the randomness of the exchange rate. Statistical techniques should be used to measure variation in the exchange rate in relation to its anticipated value. On the other hand, Levi (2005) defines foreign-exchange risk as an unexpected change in the domestic value of assets or liabilities due to an unexpected change in the exchange rate.

Foreign exchange risk refers to the losses that an international financial transaction may incur due to currency fluctuations. Foreign exchange risk can also affect investors, who trade in international

markets, and businesses engaged in the import/export of products or services to multiple countries (Moosa, 2010).

Foreign currency risk management is the process that allows firms to protect themselves from currency risk. This allows them to take control of their own competitiveness by capturing the growth opportunities resulting from buying and selling in multiple currencies (Marshall, 2000).

2.3. Theoretical review

This section is made of some theories related to the study including financial distress theory, hedging substitute's theory and managerial risk aversion theory.

2.3.1. Financial distress theory

Smith et al. (1985) found that highly levered firms with cash-flow problems or nearing bankruptcy will hedge risk to mitigate financial distress and thereby increase shareholder value (Muff et al., 2008). Hedging risk can reduce the likelihood of a firm's financial distress cost by reducing cash flow volatility. The advantage one can get by reducing this cost from risk management depends on factors such as the likelihood of encountering distress and financial distress cost. The greater the possibility of distress, the greater the benefits of hedging risks. Subsequently, researchers have employed measures to proxy for financial distress, primarily based on the borrowing capacity of the firm or leverage. The findings from Froot et al. (1993) and Smith et al. (1985) provide support to theoretical arguments that the higher the probability of financial distress, the greater is the financial derivative use (Muff et al., 2008). This theory is related to the study as the Tea exporters in Rwanda might practice the hedging risk to reduce the likelihood of a firm's financial distress cost by reducing cash flow volatility.

2.3.2. Hedging substitute's theory

Nance et al. (1993) and Froot et al. (1993) found that firms can mitigate the expected cost of financial distress and agency cost by maintaining a larger short-term liquidity position or by having a lower dividend pay-out (Muff et al., 2008). Therefore, holding liquid assets will reduce financial distress. In general, holding high liquidity can be considered as a substitute for hedging activity. This is because the cost of holding liquid assets is lower than the cost of entering into financial hedging contracts.

The underinvestment problem arises when a firm cannot make capital investments due to the high cost of external financing and lack of internally generated funds. Firms reduce their capex by roughly USD 0.35 for each dollar reduction in cash flows. Thus, a highly levered firm may be forced to take up sub-optimal investment strategies and forego profitable investment opportunities – the so-called underinvestment problem. Froot et al. (1993), Smith et al. (1985), Mayers et al. (1982), Bessembinder (1991) argue that through effective risk management, the issue of underinvestment is reduced (Charumathi & Kota, 2012). This happens when the management intends to maximize its wealth at the cost of bondholders and refuses to invest in low-risk projects. The conflict between equity and bondholders arises due to cash flow variation and the high cost of external financing, this can be resolved by hedging (Charumathi & Kota, 2012).

2.3.3. Managerial risk aversion theory

The studies done earlier found evidence that hedging increases with managerial shareholding and decreases with managerial option ownership. Graham and Rogers (2002) and Dunne et al. (2004) also find that hedging increases with managerial shareholdings only (Muff et al., 2008). These findings conclude that managerial shareholdings and stock option plans are important determinants

of hedging. Smith et al. (1985) argued that managers with more wealth invested in a firm will have greater incentives to hedge the firm's risk and that managers' compensation can influence their hedging choices. Haushalter (2000) and Jalilvand (1999) found no evidence that managerial risk aversion or shareholding affect corporate hedging (Charumathi & Kota, 2012). Ambiguity persists in analyzing the association between managerial holdings and hedging risks using derivatives.

2.4. Empirical review

This section involves the empirical results of the previous scholars about the present study. It is made of the role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks, the impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks and the effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks.

2.4.1. The role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks

Transaction exposure is the sensitivity of firm's future cash flows from contracts denominated in foreign currency to changes in exchange rate. It is a measure of change in the value of outstanding financial obligations which are denominated in foreign currency. In other words, Transaction risk refers to the impact of exchange rate changes on the value of committed cash flows i.e. future cash flows for which nominal value is known. Marshall (2000) found that US, UK and Asian Companies focus on management of transaction risk only.

Futures hedge or Currency Futures involves Currency futures contract involves a standardized contract between two parties to buy/sell an amount of currency at a fixed price on a specified date in the future and are traded on organized exchanges. Futures contracts are more liquid than forward contracts as they are traded in an organized exchange. A depreciation of currency can be hedged by selling futures and currency appreciations can be hedged by buying futures. Thus, inflow and

outflow of different currencies with respect to each other can be fixed by selling and buying currency futures, eliminating the Foreign Exchange Exposure (Abhay Kumar Gupta, 2016).

Forward hedge or Forward contracts involve an agreement between two parties to buy/sell a specific quantity of an underlying asset at a fixed price on a specified date in the future. In other words, Forward contracts are those where counterparty agrees to exchange a specified quantity of an asset at a future date for a price agreed today. These are the most commonly used foreign exchange risk management tools. The corporations can enter into forward contracts for the foreign currencies which it need for payment or which it will receive in future. Since the rate of exchange is already fixed for the future transaction, there will be no variability in the cash flows. Hence, changes that take place between the contract date and the actual transaction date does not make any impact. This will eliminate the foreign exchange exposure. The future settlement date can be an exact date or any time between two agreed dates (Chowdhry and Howe, 1999).

Currency Diversification means investing in securities denominated in different currencies. Diversification reduces the risk even if currencies are non-correlated. It will give the company global exposure, minimize foreign exchange exposure and capitalize on exchange rate disparities (Michael Papaioannou, 2006).

Currency option hedge or Currency Options are contracts which provides the holder the right to buy or sell a specified amount of currency for a specified price over a given time period. Currency options give the owner of the agreement the right to buy or sell but not an obligation. The owner of the agreement has a choice whether to use or not to use the option based on the exchange rates. He/she can choose to sell or buy the currency or let the option lapse. The writer of the option gets a price for granting this option. The price payable is known as premium. The fixed price at which the owner can sell or buy the currency is called as strike price or the exercise price. Options giving

the holder a right to buy are called call options and Options giving the holder a right to sell is called put options. It is possible to take advantage of the potential gains through currency options. For example, If an Indian business firm has to purchase capital goods from the USA in US\$ after three months, the company should buy a currency call option. There are two possibilities. First, if the dollar depreciates, then the exchange rates will be favorable as spot rate will be less than the strike price and the company can buy the US\$ at the prevailing spot rate, as it will cost less. Second, if the dollar appreciates, then the exchange rates will be unfavorable as spot rate will be more than the strike price and the company can opt to use its right and buy the US\$ at the strike price. Hence, in both the cases the company will be paying the less to buy the dollar to pay for the goods (Brown, 2001).

Furthermore, the hedging decision may be adjusted to reflect expectations of changes in exchange rates. For example, if the forward rate is a biased predictor of the spot rate expected to prevail in the future, hedgers may choose to alter their hedging strategies to accommodate this effect (see, for example, Schooley and White, 1995). Finally, the literature shows that firms tend to place more emphasis on transaction exposure than on economic and translation exposure (see, for example, Khoury and Chan, 1988). Joseph (2000) and Marshall (2000) provide survey evidence on these issues. The general conclusion arising out of these studies is that foreign exchange risk management has become one of the key factors in overall financial management, and that there is a need to measure the extent of exposure and manage it to an acceptable level (see, for example, Rawls and Smithson, 1990).

Batten et al. (1993) asserted that transaction exposure is considered as the pivot of risk management, thus this present study focuses only on transaction exposure. This study depicts transaction exposure from a viewpoint that could drive a firm's decision to practise contractual

hedging instruments. Moffett et al. (2009) explained that firms can manage their transaction exposure via contractual hedging instruments, such as forwards, swaps, money market products, futures, and options. By practicing hedging, a firm takes a stand that may counterbalance fluctuations in the prices of currencies, commodities or securities by taking a position in a contract, cash flow or an asset to guard the owner from suffering losses (Eiteman et al., 2016). As a result of FX exposure, a firm would choose to maintain a fixed exchange rate for transactions via hedging contract for protection from future unpredictable FX fluctuations.

Oxelheim and Wihlborg (1987) explained that transaction exposure is inclusive of trade receivables from exports, trade credits from imports, net foreign interest payment, and net amortisation of foreign debt. In short, transaction exposure includes all contracted cash flows that are denominated in foreign currencies.

The study by Afza & Alam (2011) pointed out that, since international transactions are becoming a crucial aspect in the trade domain, failure to report this exposure denies stakeholders from the knowledge of essential factors that may threaten the profitability and sustainability of a firm.

2.4.2. The impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks

Translation exposure is the sensitivity of firm's foreign currency denominated financial statements to changes in exchange rate. Financial statements of foreign subsidiary are to be translated in home country currency for finalizing the accounts for any given period and holding companies has to prepare consolidated financial statements. Fluctuation in exchange rates will make the value of assets and profit amount different depending on different exchange rate applied. So value of same assets and profit would be different for different period. Thus, Translation exposure arises on the consolidation of assets, liabilities and profits denominated in foreign currency in the process of

preparing consolidated accounts. It can be measured as Translation exposure = (exposed assets - exposed liabilities), this is change in exchange rate (Abhay Kumar Gupta, 2016).

Bradford Cornell and Alan C. Shapiro (1983) described how foreign exchange risk can be managed. In their article “The Management of Foreign Exchange risk”, identified that in many realistic situations, the economic effects of randomness of exchange rate are different from those predicted by the various measures of translation exposure. It emphasizes the distinctions between the currency of location, the currency of denomination and the currency of determination of a business. They argued that a market-based approach be followed in international financial planning.

Fok et al. (1997) have found that hedging not only reduces variability in earnings but it also increases firm value. They found that hedging not only decreases the chances of financial distress but also the agency costs of debt and the costs of equity. Chowdhry and Howe (1999) argue that firms use financial instruments to hedge short term exposure and for managing long-run operating exposure, they use long-term strategy adjustments (i.e., operational hedges).

Niclas hagelin and bengt pramborg (2002) investigated the effectiveness of currency derivatives and foreign denominated debt in reducing foreign exchange exposure. The results were positive.

Sathya Swaroop Debasish (2008) studied the foreign exchange risk management practices of 501 nonbanking Indian firms to identify the techniques which they use to hedge their foreign exchange risk. It was revealed that volatility and reduction in cash flows was the rationale behind hedging. The techniques used by Indian firms are forward contracts, swaps and cross-currency options. Confused perception about derivative use, technical and administrative constraints and fear of high

cost were found to be the main reasons of not pursuing any foreign exchange risk management technique. The paper discusses the various foreign exchange risk management techniques.

Jain, Yadav, and Rastogi (2009) discusses and compares the foreign exchange risk management strategies and interest rate risk management strategies followed by public companies, private business houses and foreign companies operating in India. All the risks are not managed. Management of these companies operating in India are of opinion that amount of exposure accruing to these do not require to be specially managed.

Peter mbabazi mbabazize, twesige daniel and issac emukule ekise (2014) found that exporting firms in Uganda had a significant relationship between currency risk transfer strategies and gross profit margin, net profit margin and sales growth.

Purchasing currency swaps or a currency swap involves an agreement between two parties to exchange a series of cash flows in one currency for a series of cash flows in another currency, at agreed intervals over an agreed period. This is done to convert a liability in one currency to some other currency. Its purpose is to raise funds denominated in other currency. One party holding one currency swaps it for another currency held by other party. Each party would pay the interest for the exchanged currency at regular interval of time during the term of the loan. At maturity or at the termination of the loan period each party would re-exchange the principal amount in two currencies (Brown, 2001).

An early study by Dufey (1972) discussed how the depreciation of a foreign currency against a group's reporting currency could generate the confrontational situation discussed in Section 2 of the present study. Because of accounting translation practices, the depreciation of the reporting currency of a foreign affiliate may reduce the amount of reported earnings of that affiliate which

are included in the consolidated results of the group. But, the currency depreciation may actually improve the economic competitiveness, and ultimate financial profitability of the affiliate. Because of the conspicuousness of translation adjustments in consolidated earnings statements, Dufey comments on how potentially profitable direct investment opportunities, in countries with unstable currency histories, might well be foregone.

Another early study by Aggarwal et al. (1978) examined the effect of FASB No. 8 on reported financial statements of U.S. based multinational firms. Aggarwal concluded that the 'procrustean' accounting adjustments required by FASB No. 8 were not likely to reflect the economic reality of the underlying changes in exchange rates. Therefore, reported accounting figures were likely to misrepresent the economic reality of the firm's exposure to exchange rate risk, unless they were supplemented with other detailed information. This view was supported by O'Brien (1997) who asserted that accounting methods might either underestimate or overestimate the true economic exposure, in terms of changes in some microeconomic factors. These factors include such things as the elasticity of exchange rate changes or the responsiveness of firm level operating profits to changes in exchange rate.

In a similar vein, Garlicki et al. (1987) argued, in support of FASB No. 52, that, since a firm's accounting exposure is not necessarily aligned with its economic exposure, reported translation gains or losses are merely 'cosmetic changes,' and not necessarily related to changes in the future cash-flows of the firm. Thus, eliminating these gains or losses may lead to higher quality earnings. However, although SFAS No. 52 may have placated irritated executives of multinational firms, some academic researchers have been critical of the propriety of reporting foreign currency translation gains or losses in shareholders' equity. For example, Beaver and Wolfson (1984) illustrate that accounting translation gains and losses capture, at least, some of the economic factors

behind the interplay of interest rates and exchange rates, and, therefore, to exclude those factors from earnings can result in misleading earnings-based performance evaluations of the foreign operations of multinational firms. Beaver and Wolfson also criticise SFAS No. 52 regarding its requirement that items recorded at historical cost in the balance sheets of foreign subsidiaries must be translated at current exchange rates. The authors conclude that this practice produces accounting numbers which are not interpretable and serves to compound the bias produced by SFAS No. 8 in the translation of long-term monetary items.

As regards the empirical research evidence on the relationship between reported foreign currency translation adjustments and firm value, two distinct groupings have emerged. The first group of empirical studies either to report significant evidence of a relationship between foreign currency translation adjustments and firm value, or only partial evidence of such a relationship. In a study seeking to further explore the findings of an earlier study (Bartov and Bondar, 1994), Bartov and Bondar (1995) investigate the possibility that the change in reporting requirements from SFAS No. 8 to SFAS No. 52 enhance the market's ability to assess the impact of movements in exchange rates on firm values. As in the case of their 1994 study, Bartov and Bondar (1995) found no evidence of a contemporaneous relationship between exchange rate movements and firm value. However, after controlling for firm size, the study did produce evidence that, in the case of those firms choosing the foreign currency as the functional currency of their overseas subsidiaries, the change in reporting regime resulted in the disappearance of a lagged response of firm value to movement in exchange rates. With specific regard to those firms choosing the foreign currency as the functional currency, the authors interpreted their results as evidence of the translation reporting requirements of FASB No. 52 facilitating prediction by investors of the impact of changes in exchange rates on the market value of U.S. firms with foreign operations.

Using data from a sample of U.S. multinational firms, Bartov (1997) investigated the value relevance of translation adjustments related to alternative translation methods. Bartov's results indicated that the introduction of SFAS No. 52 resulted in significant enhancement in the valuation relevance of the accounting numbers associated with the restatement of a foreign operation's financial statements. However, this significant enhancement applies only to that group of firms, whose subsidiaries used a foreign currency as a functional currency. For those firms which chose the U.S. dollar as the functional currency for their subsidiaries, no significant association was found between currency translation adjustments and changes in stock price. Bartov's results, regarding the value enhancement being restricted to those firms choosing foreign currencies as the functional currencies, corroborate the findings of earlier studies by Griffin and Castanias (1987) and Collins and Salatka (1993).

Following Dechow (1994), Dhaliwal et al. (1999) employed the return to earnings association approach to examine whether the summary measure of firm performance, the Statement of Income and Comprehensive Income, required under SFAS No. 130 to be included in a firm's primary financial statements, is more strongly associated with returns/market value, or better predicts future cash flows/income than the net income alone. As noted previously, one of the three component adjustments of comprehensive income is the change in the cumulative foreign currency translation adjustments. The study found no evidence that comprehensive income is more strongly associated with returns/market value or is a better predictor of future cash-flows/income than net income. The only component of comprehensive income found to improve the association between income and returns, was the marketable securities adjustment. These results suggest that, as an element of comprehensive income, foreign currency translation adjustments are not value relevant. This conclusion is consistent with Dee (1999).

The second empirical studies group does provide evidence of a relationship between translation adjustments and firm value. Using an amended version of an early model developed by Litzenger and Rao (1971), which views the market value of a firm as a capitalisation of earnings, adjusted for both systematic risk and growth, Callaghan & Bazaz (1992) tested the hypothesis of whether equity translation adjustments, such as those prescribed in SFAS No. 52, are considered by investors as a component of consolidated income. Although Callaghan and Bazaz's study was not designed as a test of the value relevance of translation adjustments, per se, their results are relevant to the current study since they found evidence, via the capitalisation of reported earnings, consistent with the hypothesis that equity translation adjustments are viewed by investors as a component of income.

Soo and Soo (1994) used an abnormal returns model to examine the effect of accounting exposure on firm value for a sample of 235 multinational U.S. firms, for two seven-year sample periods: 1976 – 1982 and 1981 – 1987. This design allowed the authors to test whether any market valuation of foreign exchange gains and losses was different between the periods covered by SFAS No. 8 and SFAS No. 52. It also allowed for the testing of whether any market reaction to translation adjustments differed from the reaction to transaction adjustments or other earnings. Those firms which exclusively chose the U.S. dollar as the functional currency of their foreign affiliates were excluded from the sample. The results of the study were consistent with the market valuing foreign exchange adjustments reported in income, under both accounting standards. In addition, the results indicated market valuation of the translation adjustments reported under stockholders' equity under SFAS No. 52. However, the sensitivity of firm value to the adjustments reported in stockholders' equity was smaller than the sensitivity to other earnings. This result led the authors

to suggest that translation adjustments should be reported separately from other earnings and from transaction gains and losses.

Martin et al. (1998) tested the hypotheses of whether the translated shareholders' equity and the translated earnings figures affected the excess return of the firm. Using a sample of 168 U.S. multinational firms (1,071 sample observations) with foreign operations primarily based in Europe, for the period 1987 – 1993, the authors regressed the monthly stock returns of each individual firm on the returns of both the European and the U.S. stock markets. The saved coefficients from this regression were then used to calculate the monthly abnormal return for each firm, which, in turn formed the dependent variable in a cross-sectional time series regression, with the independent variables including the translated shareholders' equity and the translated earnings. The results showed evidence of a significant relationship between the values of the firms in the sample, as quantified by excess returns, and: (1) overall operating earnings, (2) translation effect on earnings, (3) translation effect on shareholders' equity. On the basis of these results the authors concluded that accounting exposure had a significant impact on firm value.

Using a sample of U.S. multinational manufacturing companies, Louis (2003) examines the relation between the foreign currency translation adjustments and firm value. The relevant study period is 1985 – 2001, with 4,972 sample observations. A four-factor regression model is implemented to examine the impact of foreign translation adjustment and net income on the firm's actual stock returns. The author includes two control variables in his model: transaction gain/loss and foreign income tax. Based on a prior economic analysis, Louis hypothesized that positive foreign translation adjustments of the manufacturing firms in his sample would be associated with decreases in firm value. The results of the study were consistent with this hypothesis, prompting

the author to voice concerns about an ‘accounting income computation that recognizes a positive translation adjustment as an increase in value.

The conflicting results of previous studies have prompted us to investigate the question of the value relevance of translation adjustments in Tea exporters businesses in Rwanda.

2.4.3. The effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks

Debt financing or foreign debts are an effective way to hedge the foreign exchange exposure. This is supported by the International Fischer Effect relationship. For example, a company is expected to receive a fixed amount of Euros at a future date. There is a possibility that the company can experience loss if the domestic currency appreciates against the Euros. To hedge this, company can take a loan in Euros for the same time period and convert the foreign currency into domestic currency at the spot exchange rate. And when the company receives Euros, it can pay off its loan in Euros. Hence the company can completely eliminate its foreign exchange exposure (Sathya Swaroop Debasish, 2008).

Matching refers to the process in which a company matches its currency inflows with its currency outflows with respect to amount and timing. When a company has receipts and payments in same foreign currency due at same time, it can simply match them against each other. Hedging is required for unmatched portion of foreign currency cash flows. This kind of operation is referred to as natural matching. Parallel matching is another possibility. When gains in one foreign currency are expected to be offset by losses in another, if the movements in two currencies are parallel is called parallel matching (Chowdhry and Howe, 1999).

Cross-currency swap or Cross Hedging means taking opposing position in two positively correlated currencies. It can be used when hedging of a particular foreign currency is not possible.

Even though hedging is done in a different currency, the effects would remain the same and hence cross hedging is an important technique that can be used by companies (Abhay Kumar Gupta, 2016).

Chowdhry and Howe (1999) developed a theoretical model to analyse the conditions for operational hedging by multinational corporations. They argued that using only financial hedges cannot effectively manage the firm's operating exposure. Alternatively, they suggested that operational hedges are the most effective way to manage long-run operating exposure. However, Lim and Wang (2001) showed that financial hedging and operational hedging are more complements to, rather than substitute for each other. Their study argued that financial hedging can be used to reduce the common component of profit variability, while operational hedging (geographic diversification) can reduce firm-specific risk exposures. Therefore, these theoretical studies argued that using operational hedging may not be sufficient for a firm to reduce foreign currency exposures for some firms. Consequently, they suggested that operational hedging becomes more effective if the firm combines it with financial hedges.

Many empirical studies investigated the impact of the combined use of currency derivatives and operational hedges on the firms' foreign exchange exposures. These studies have reported that the proxy for the use of currency derivatives (financial hedging) decreases the exposure. However, mixed results have been reported in terms of the relationship between operational hedging proxies and the exposure. In terms of the mixed results, the first group reported that the firm's foreign diversification foreign subsidiaries decrease exposure, while the proxies for geographical dispersion of foreign subsidies increase exposure (Allayannis et al, 2001). However, the second group of studies reported that diversification of the firm's foreign operations increases the exposure, while both geographical diversification and dispersion of these foreign subsidiaries

decreases the firm's exposure (Carter et al., 2001, Kim et al., 2005). In relation to the substitute or complementary relationship between those two hedging strategies, some studies reported a complementary relationship between those two hedging strategies (Kim et al., 2005).

The first study was adopted by Simkins and Laux (1997), who investigated the impact of the use of currency derivatives and operational hedging on the foreign exchange exposure at both the firm and industry levels. It used a sample of the largest 395 US. Multinational firms in 1993. After estimating the exposure coefficients using Jorion's (1990) augmented model, the authors ran a cross-sectional regression model to test for the impact of the combined use of currency derivatives and operational hedges with respect to an interaction variable (measure by multiplying the proxy for currency derivatives and operational hedging) and firm size, on the foreign exchange exposure. They measured currency derivatives by a dummy variable, which took 1 if the firm used currency derivatives or zero otherwise. Their results indicated that, at firm-level and industry-level, firms with higher foreign sales ratio (foreign operational involvement) were more likely to be exposed to currency risk. However, diversification across multiple lines of business can potentially reduce currency exposure. Therefore, they found that the combined use of financial and operational hedging was associated with foreign currency exposure reduction.

Allayannis et al., (2001) examined the impact of operational hedges of 220 U.S firms on foreign exchange exposure for the year 1993. Its contribution to the literature was the documenting of the importance of operational hedges jointly with currency derivatives as significant determinants of exchange rate risk. In terms of currency derivative use, which was negatively associated with the exposure, the study reported mixed results for the geographical dispersion of foreign subsidiaries across countries and regions. They found an inverse relationship between the firms' number of foreign subsidiaries across countries and regions and currency exposure. However, a positive

relationship existed between the dispersion of the firm's foreign subsidiaries across countries and regions and exposures.

Carter et al., (2001) investigated the effects of the combined use of operational hedging and currency derivatives on the exposure coefficients. They contributed to the literature by including the firms' ownership structure variables to their cross-sectional regression model, as they divided a firm's ownership to four separate variables: the shares owned by insiders, block-holders, the squared value of the insider's ownership variable, and institutions, and for the impact of long-term leverage on firm's currency exposures. The study reported that the combined use of operational and financial hedges was associated with the exposure reduction.

Operational hedging strategy of U.S. high technology firms and how this hedging is related to financial hedging was examined by Gleason et al., (2005). The sample for their study was consisted of 216 firms of which 108 firms were high technology operationally-hedged firms and a size and industry matched sample of 108 non-operational hedged firms. Their study contributed to the literature by testing whether the use of financial and operational has an impact on the impact of the means had a net importer, while a firm with negative exposure (net exporter). They found that both operational hedging and financial hedging were associated with reducing the foreign exchange exposure. In addition, they also found that operational hedging was complementary to financial hedging.

To sum up, although these studies use the same research methodology procedure, they report conflicting results, especially, in relation to the effect of operational hedging on exposure. The conflicting results have prompted us to investigate the question on the impact of the combined use of the currency derivatives and operational hedging on the foreign exchange exposure in Rwandan

context. Strategies. This is since operational and financial hedging strategies are used for managing different types of risk exposures, i.e., operational hedging for long-term exposure (economic exposure) and financial hedging for short-term exposure (transaction exposure). In addition, the other interest of our work is to examine whether the use of currency derivatives is a complement to operational hedging in reducing the exposure to foreign exchange risk. This is as to our knowledge, no empirical work, using data for Rwanda exports has been published to date.

2.5. Research gap

The studies presented in literature review focused on various countries but, there is few researches conducted for Rwanda about hedging foreign currency exposure and foreign currency risks. It is for this reason that, it is evident that this research must fill that knowledge gap in the literature.

There is a knowledge gap as some researches were conducted on the effect of Exchange Rate Fluctuation on Rwandan Tea Price and Exports (Kabayiza et al., 2019), but all these previous studies didn't point out the foreign currency hedging approaches adopted by the tea exporters in order to manage this problem of foreign exchange exposure. In this way, this study established the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk control with a case study of tea exporters in Rwanda.

2.6. Conceptual framework

This part indicates the A written or visual representation of an expected relationship between variables. The mentioned variables are simply the characteristics or properties that the study want to study. The following conceptual framework is generally developed based on literature review of existing studies and theories about the topic. The following figure presents the study variables including the dependent variable and independent variables.

Independent variables

Dependent variable

Hedging Foreign Exchange Exposures

Foreign currency risks

Source: The researcher, 2022

FIGURE 1: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The conceptual framework indicates that the Foreign Currency Risks is a dependent variable of the study which is explained by Transaction risks (Variance), Translation risks (Variance) and Operating risks (Variance). The independent variables of the study are Hedging Transaction exposure, Hedging Translation exposure and Hedging Operating exposure. In fact, the study indicated the relationship between dependent variable and independent variables.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

This study dealt with analyzing the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk in tea exporters in Rwanda, with a case study of Five Tea Exporters in Rwanda. In conducting this study, different methods and techniques were used. This chapter presents the methods and techniques that will be used in data collection and data analysis. The chapter provides full explanation of the research design, which is the plan, structure, and strategy of investigation conceived so as to test the hypotheses of the study.

3.2. Research Design

According to Peter Odera and Okenyi (2006), a study design is a plan or a blue print which shows how data required for the solution of a problem that research is studying were collected and analyzed. The present research will respond to the descriptive and correlational research designs since data were provided by questionnaires and interviews. Thus, it was based on qualitative methods.

The nature of the research is analytical research it seeks to explain t analyzing the hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk. The type of the investigation is the relation, as it tried to observe whether the hedging foreign exchange exposure has a significant impact on for foreign currency risk minimization. This was achieved by showing the existence, direction, strength and greater significance of the relation. This study concerns the firms in the question. This study used primary data on hedging foreign exchange exposure and foreign currency risk for the period 2022. The data were collected from all the top five Tea Exporters in Rwanda. The researcher entered data into SPSS version 22.0 and Microsoft Excel to derive statistics for the data.

3.3 The population of the study

According to Bryman, A. (1988), the population is a universal object over which study should be conducted. The ideal research technique would be to collect data from the whole population; this would assure maximal coverage of the group being studied.

The entire group of persons, things, or measures with some common observable features that a researcher intends to examine is referred to as a population (Kothari, 2004).

Under this study, the research population was composed by all employees in financial department in the five top Tea Exporters in Rwanda. The total population of the study is 50 staff working in financial department in the top five selected tea exporters in Rwanda. The following table describes the total population of the study.

Table 1: Population of the study

Tea Exporter Companies	Number of employees in Financial department
Rwanda Mountain Tea	11
SORWATHE Tea	9
Karongi Tea Factory Limited	12
Rwanda Tea	10
Gisovu Tea Estate	8
Total	50

Source: Done by the Researcher, 2022

3.4. Sampling technique

The method by which a researcher aims to pick a sample from the total population is referred to as sampling methodology (Kothari, 2004). Universal sampling is the sample technique that will be employed in our investigation.

The width of the topic under the study, population provided that it was not so wide. Thus, the technique that was used in this research was universal sampling. Universal sampling refers to the selection of sample where all the elements in the population are selected as respondents for the research. In this way, all the 50 employees in financial department have been involved in the study.

3.5. Data collection Techniques and Tools

The following are the instruments were used in data collection, including:

3.5.1. Questionnaire

A questionnaire, according to Nachmias (1976), is a series of questions intended to obtain information from respondents. It's also used to refer to a series of self-administered questions. In this study, the questionnaire included both closed-ended and open-ended questions to allow respondents to convey their overall opinions while also allowing them to provide their own replies to the questions. In this study, a set of question was given to the staff in financial departments in the top five Tea exporters in Rwanda.

3.5.2. Interview

An interview, according to Kerlinger (1964), is a face-to-face interaction between an interviewer and a responder with the goal of gathering information. Interviews are conducted in person or over the phone, with the researcher soliciting replies verbally. The interviewer and the responders met

face to face to conduct the interview. It was carried out with the goal of gathering data on the impact of hedging foreign exchange exposure for foreign currency risk control. Interview was conducted with the 5 Directors Managers in the selected top five tea exporters in Rwanda.

3.5.3. Documentary technique

Kenneth (1978) defined documentation as the careful reading, understanding and analyzing the written documents of some purpose rather than social research. They are records of past events that are written or printed. The researcher used documentation to analyze the hedging foreign exchange exposure and foreign currency risk in the five top Tea Exporters in order to get secondary data that were served to the achievement of study objectives. The researcher used data obtained from the case studies annual Reports during the period of the study.

3.6. Method of data analysis

Data analysis entails the organizing and interpretation of data collected in relation to each study aim (ULK research guidelines, 2020). The qualitative and quantitative techniques to data analysis have been used in this study. Explanatory approaches for qualitative data and statistical procedures (mean, standard deviation, etc.) for quantitative data are among the methods or techniques have been utilized in data analysis.

The study hypotheses were formulated in the following ways;

$H_0: b_1 = b_2 = 0$ (Null hypothesis)

$H_1: \text{At least } b_1 \neq 0 \text{ or } b_2 \neq 0 \text{ or both } a \text{ and } b \neq 0$ (Alternative hypothesis)

This was the hypothesis for F-Test is used to test the significance of the model. In this context,

H_0 stated that the model is not significant and H_1 stated that the model is significant.

Another hypothesis was for T-Test which was used in testing if there is a relation between the dependent variable and independent variables. The hypotheses were formulated in the followings ways:

H₀: There is no relationship between independent variables and Dependent variable.

H₁: There is no relationship between independent variables and Dependent variable.

For data analysis, descriptive statistics were employed. Mean, maximum, minimum, and percentages are examples of descriptive statistics.

3.6.1 Mean

The mean is calculated by dividing the total number of all identified results from the trial by the total number of occurrences.

The mean is calculated as follow:

$\bar{x}$ represents the mean and x represents the detected results from the trial. $\bar{x} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$
(Ghahramani, 2008).

TABLE 2: EVALUATION OF MEAN

Mean	Interpretation
1.00-1.49	Strongly Disagree
1.50-2.49	Disagree
2.50-3.49	Neutral
3.50-4.49	Agree
4.5-5.500	Strongly Agree

Source: (Berman and Saunders, 2008)

3.6.2 Standard Deviations (σ)

The standard deviation is a statistical number utilized to know the quality of the data that are distributed to the average. By formula, the standard deviation is computed as follows:

$$\sigma = \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} (x - \mu)^2} \text{ (Ghahramani, 2008)}$$

TABLE 3: EVALUATION OF STANDARD DEVIATION

Standard deviation	Quality of data
Standard deviation <0.5	Low dispersion of data (homogeneity)
Standard deviation >0.5	Big dispersion of data (heterogeneity)

Source: (Saunders, 2008)

3.6.3 Correlation

Correlation is used in this study to show the statistical relationship between two variables. Thus, we were able to see the relationship between Hedging foreign exposure and currency risks control in the Top five Tea Exporters in Rwanda. The following are the statistical guidelines we based on to show the correlation coefficient.

TABLE 4: EVALUATION OF CORRELATION

Correlation coefficient	Interpretation
r=1	Perfect linear correlation
0.9<r<1	Strong linear correlation
0.7<r<0.9	High correlation
0.5<r<0.6	Moderate correlation
0<r<0.5	Weak correlation
r=0	No correlation

Source: (Franklin, 2009)

Apart from the methods stated above the following methods were also used in data analysis and interpretation;

3.6.4. Historical method

This method was useful to know the evolution of risks control due to hedging foreign exposure in the top five tea exporters in Rwanda.

3.6.5. Comparative method

This method played the role into making comparison between the risks control due to hedging foreign exposure within several years.

3.6.6. Analytical method

This method was used to analyze the data collected: it concerned the transformation of findings collection from the field into system of categories and verification of data. This involved coding, editing and tabulation.

Kerlinger (1964) described editing as the act of identifying and eliminating mistakes in completed interview schedules and questionnaires. The researcher modified the data to ensure that it is comprehensive, accurate, uniform, and understandable.

According to Guy Cumberbatch (1973), coding is categorizing responses into meaningful categories in order to reveal their key patterns. The researcher coded data that is simple to comprehend. Coding was done by creating coding frames depending on the questions given. The answers to the specific questions were logged, resulting in coding patterns that were used to create coding frames. Frequencies counts were performed once the coding frames have been constructed to make tabulation easier.

Tabulation, according to Nachimias (1976), is the process of arranging data into statistical tables, such as percentage and frequency of replies to certain queries. The tabulation procedure entails entering data into statistical tables and calculating the frequency answers for each variable, which displayed the number of replies to popular questions that are accurate and their estimated percentages. After the data has been revised and processed, it was integrated into tables for statistical analysis. SPSS 22.0 version software and Excel 2013 version software were used to create these tables, frequencies, and statistics.

3.7. Validity and reliability tests

Validity is defined as the extent to which the instrument measures what it purports to measure (Bell, E. and Bryman, A. 2007). Content validity pertains to the degree which the instrument fully assesses or measure the construct of interest. The questionnaires and interviews were carefully prepared and analyzed in order to get relevant data on hedging foreign exposure and risks control. This was done in order to enhance its validity and accuracy of data collected for the study.

The reliability of a research instrument concerns the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated trials. Although unreliability is always present to a certain extent, there was a good deal of consistency in the results of a quality instrument gathered at different times. The tendency toward consistency found in repeated measurements is referred to as reliability (Bell, E. and Bryman, A. 2007). The research was reliable as well as the findings get from the Directors Managers involved are the same with the findings get from the employees involved in the study.

3.8. Limitation of the study

Though good work it is, this research may be impeded by inaccessibility to very expensive books and papers. Some of the books that may not be in our disposition and not accessed, as they are

costly and not affordable while the book might contain relevant information. Time is the second major constraint as this was limited since the researcher has many tasks (studies, jobs and researches). Nevertheless, the researcher tried to do her best so as to overcome those challenges positively.

3.8. Ethical considerations

Ethical considerations in research, according to Bell and Bryman, (2007), include describing the substance of the research and what would be expected of participants, as well as how informed permission was acquired and confidentiality was ensured.

This research was conducted in a way that the ethical considerations for research including Privacy and confidentiality, social and culture sensitivity research merit, conflict audience, respect for property right even data retention was taken into consideration.

CHAPTER 4: PRESENTATION OF THE FINDINGS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter provides the answers to the research questions and tests of the hypotheses. Each research question has been verified according to the primary data obtained from 50 people who work in financial department and the general managers in the top five tea exporters in Rwanda in the selected five tea exporters companies in Rwanda. The study involved two categories of questions including questions related to the personal identification and questions related to the study objectives.

4.2. Profile of the respondents

The researcher was interested in knowing the identification of the respondents in terms of gender of the respondents, age of the respondents, marital status of the respondents, educational level of the respondents, Tea Exporter Company of the respondents and time period of the respondents working with tea Exporter Company.

4.2.1. Gender of the respondents

The gender of the respondents has been investigated so as to know the gender of the respondents. The researcher evaluated gender differences in order to examine the views of both males and females about the impact of foreign currency exposure on foreign currency risks control. Table 5 depicts the details about the issue.

TABLE 5: GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	32	64.0	64.0	64.0
Female	18	36.0	36.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors’ calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The researcher was interested in knowing the gender of the respondents. The findings in table 5 indicated that 64% of the staff’s respondents were males and 36% of the respondents were female. This implies that the research was gender sensitive as it has involved both males and females. This implies that gender balance was respected even if female were slightly less than male due to the presence of respondents that the researcher met on the field. Although, this helped the researcher to get different ideas as views of females and males are sometimes different.

4.2.2. Age of the respondents

The age of the respondents has been investigated so as to know the age group of the respondents. It was necessary as the research wanted to know views and opinions from people of various age about of hedging foreign currency exposure and foreign currency risk control. The following table describes the age groups of the respondents.

TABLE 6: AGE OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 21- 30 years	12	24.0	24.0	24.0
31- 40 years	20	40.0	40.0	64.0
41- 50 years	11	22.0	22.0	86.0
51 years and above	7	14.0	14.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors’ calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The table 6 indicated that 40% of the respondents are between 31-40 years, 22% of the respondents are between 41-50 years, 24% of the respondents are between 21-30years and only 14% of the respondents were 51 years and above. This has shown that majority of respondents were mature, so, for this reason the researchers pretended to get valid responses from the respondents.

4.2.3. Marital status of the respondents

It was deemed necessary and important to collect data while considering marital status of respondents. This helped the researcher to analyse which category of respondents in terms of marital status. In an attempt to ascertain respondents' marital status of respondents, they were requested to provide their marital status of respondents. Therefore, results are summarized in the following Table.

TABLE 7: MARITAL STATUS OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Single	18	36.0	36.0	36.0
Married	27	54.0	54.0	90.0
Divorced	2	4.0	4.0	94.0
Widower	3	6.0	6.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors' calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

About marital status, 54% of the respondents were married, 36% of the respondents were single and only 6% of the respondents were widower and 4% of the respondents were divorced. Having different categories of people contributes more on research findings validation.

4.2.4. Educational level of the respondents

The education profile reveals the level of educational attainments of respondents which could be used to indicate the potential employability that will be instrument deemed to influence and provide real information on the present study. The level of education of respondents implies that they should have accurate information about the study topic. The following table describes more about respondents' level of education.

TABLE 8: EDUCATIONAL LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Advanced level (A2)	9	18.0	18.0	18.0
Bachelors' degree (A0)	24	48.0	48.0	66.0
Masters' degree	8	16.0	16.0	82.0
Graduate with a professional course Graduate with a professional course	9	18.0	18.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors' calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

Concerning educational level of the respondents, majority of the respondents (48%) achieved Bachelor's degree level of education, 18% of the respondents completed Advanced level of education, 18% graduated with a professional course and the master's level is represented by 16% of the respondents. Thus, for the present research, the educational level of respondents is important from the standpoint of potential to give their opinion on effects of hedging foreign currency exposure on foreign currency risk control because it generally agreed that the level of education is in line with the level of knowledge and the understanding of phenomena.

4.2.5. Tea Exporter Company of the respondents

The researcher was interested in knowing the tea exporters companies in which respondents belong. The following table provides more details on the Tea Exporter Company of the respondents.

TABLE 9: TEA EXPORTER COMPANY OF THE RESPONDENTS

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Rwanda Mountain Tea	11	22.0	22.0	22.0
SORWATHE Tea	9	18.0	18.0	40.0
Karongi Tea Factory Limited	12	24.0	24.0	64.0
Rwanda Tea	10	20.0	20.0	84.0
Gisovu Tea Estate	8	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors' calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The findings from the table 9 indicated that 22% of the respondents belonged to Rwanda Mountain Tea, 24% of the respondents belonged to Karongi Tea Factory Limited, 20% belong to Rwanda Tea, 18% of the participants belonged to SORWATRHE Tea and 16% of the participants belonged to Gisovu Tea Estate. Having the participants from various Tea Exporters Companies increased the accuracy and consistency of the study findings.

4.2.6. Time period of respondents working with the Tea Exporter Company

The researcher was interested in presenting the time period of respondents working with the Tea Exporter Company. The time period of respondents working with the Tea Exporter Company is a good indicator of the findings validity and worthiness. The following table points out more information about the time period of respondents working with the Tea Exporter Company.

TABLE 10: TIME PERIOD OF RESPONDENTS WORKING WITH THE TEA EXPORTER COMPANY

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1 - 3 years	12	24.0	24.0	24.0
4- 6 years	20	40.0	40.0	64.0
7 years and above	18	36.0	36.0	100.0
Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, authors’ calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The table 10 indicated that 40% of the respondents have been in Tea Exporters Company for a period between 4-6 years, 24% of the respondents have in Tea Exporters Company for a period between 1-3 years and 36% of the respondents have been in Tea Exporters Company for a period of 7 years and above. Provided that the sampled respondents have in Tea Exporters Company for a long period of time, it is very true to confirm that the provided information were accurate and valid.

4.3. Descriptive statistics

Some descriptive statistics were conducted in order to provide basic information about variables in a dataset to highlight potential relationships between variables. In this context, the study indicated the maximum, minimum, mean, standard deviation and correlations coefficients among variables. The following part provides more details on the descriptive statistics of independents variables and dependent variable.

4.3.1. Descriptive statistics on the hedging Transaction exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies

The following table contains various statements on the role of the hedging Transaction exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies. For each statement the maximum, minimum, mean and standard deviations were provided.

TABLE 11: THE ROLE OF HEDGING TRANSACTION EXPOSURE ON FOREIGN CURRENCY RISKS FOR TEA EXPORTERS

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The company uses Forward contracts techniques in order to control foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.79179
The company uses Futures contracts techniques in order to minimize foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2600	.66425
The company uses Money market hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.72843
The company uses Currency option hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2200	.64807
The company uses risk shifting techniques effectively in order to minimize foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2400	.55549
The company uses currency risk sharing techniques effectively in order to avoid foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1800	.62890
The company uses leading and lagging techniques in order to reduce foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1000	.76265
The company uses rein voicing centers techniques in order to manage foreign currency risks	50	4.00	5.00	4.2800	.45356
Hedging Transaction exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.63888
Hedging Transaction exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets	50	2.00	5.00	4.2200	.64807
Valid N (listwise)	50				

Source: Primary data, authors' calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The above table examined the first objective of exploring the role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree. The Table 11 indicated that the investigated respondents were 50 and about the role of the hedging Transaction exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies, the minimum is 2 which means Disagree and the maximum is 5 which means strongly agree.

The respondents confirmed that the company uses the Forward contracts techniques in order to control foreign currency risks as the mean was 4.1600 which means agree. Futures contracts techniques are also used in order to minimize foreign currency risks as it was indicated by the mean of 4.2600 which means Agree. The company uses Money market hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks as it was confirmed by majority of the respondents, the evidence is the mean of 4.2000 which implies agree. In all the statements given above the standard deviation was greater than 0.5 which means participants heterogeneity in answering to the questions.

The company uses Currency option hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks, with the mean of 4.2400 which means agree. The respondents from the selected five tea companies confirmed also that the company uses risk shifting techniques effectively in order to minimize foreign currency risks in tea exporters Companies in Rwanda. With the mean of 4.1800 it was indicated clearly that the company uses currency risk sharing techniques effectively in order to avoid foreign currency risks as it was confirmed by many respondents of the study participants. The standard deviation which is greater than 0.5 means heterogeneity, but having heterogeneity is not a problem as the mean indicates the common views of the study participants.

The study participants agree that the company uses leading and lagging techniques in order to reduce foreign currency risks, it was clearly indicated by the mean of 4.1000 which stands for

agree. The company uses rein voicing centers techniques in order to manage foreign currency risks as it was shown by all the respondents of the study participants. Many respondents agree that hedging Transaction exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit. This was approved by the mean of 4.2000 which means agree. Hedging Transaction exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets as many of the study participants have confirmed the statement, this was affirmed by the mean of 4.2200 which means agree. The mean represents the shared opinions of the study participants, therefore having heterogeneity is not a concern if the standard deviation is bigger than 0.5.

The above findings have been also confirmed by the primary data obtained from the interview and other further statistical analysis conducted. Within discussion of the results the study pointed also out what other previous scholars revealed on the role of the hedging Transaction exposure for foreign currency risks control.

4.3.2. Descriptive statistics on the hedging Translation exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies.

The following table contains various statements on the role of the hedging Translation exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies. For each statement the maximum, minimum, mean and standard deviations were provided. The table examines the second objective of exploring the role of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree.

TABLE 12: THE IMPACT OF HEDGING TRANSLATION EXPOSURE ON FOREIGN CURRENCY RISKS FOR TEA EXPORTERS

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The company uses Purchasing currency swaps techniques in order to control foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.0800	.89989
The company purchases foreign currency to be put on the foreign currency account so as to be able to meet outside country expenses at lower cost	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.72843
The Company uses Hedging through futures contracts techniques so as to control foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.72843
There is no challenge due to gains on forward contracts used to hedge translation exposure that are taxed	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.71027
Current and non-current methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.63888
Monetary and Non-monetary methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure	50	2.00	5.00	4.1000	.76265
Using a combination of the above hedging techniques is an effective way of controlling translation exposure	50	2.00	5.00	4.0600	.81841
Current rate methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure	50	2.00	5.00	4.2400	.55549
Hedging Translation exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.71027
Hedging Translation exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets	50	2.00	5.00	4.1800	.71969
Valid N (listwise)	50				

Source: Primary data, authors' calculations using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

The Table 12 indicated that the investigated respondents were 50 and about the role of the hedging Translation exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies, the minimum is 2 which means Disagree and the maximum is 5 which means strongly agree. The following paragraphs describes more the role of the hedging Translation exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies.

The findings from the table 12 indicated that the company uses purchasing currency swaps techniques in order to control foreign currency risks. This was indicated by the big percentage of the respondents who have agree the statement as the mean is 4.0800. The company purchases foreign currency to be put on the foreign currency account so as to be able to meet outside country expenses at lower cost as the mean is 4.200 which means agree. With the mean of 4.200 which stands for agree it was clearly indicated that the Company uses Hedging through futures contracts techniques so as to control foreign currency risks as it was affirmed by many of the respondents. For all the statements the standard deviation is greater than 0.5 which stands for heterogeneity.

The study participants agree that there is no challenge due to gains on forward contracts used to hedge translation exposure that are taxed in their tea exporters companies due to the mean of 4.1600. Current and non-current methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure as it was indicated by the mean of 4.2000 which means agree. Monetary and Non-monetary methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure as many of the study participants have agreed. The values of standard deviation within all assertions indicated absence of homogeneity in answers.

Using a combination of the above hedging techniques is an effective way of controlling translation exposure, this was affirmed by many of the study respondents from the five selected tea Exporters Companies in Rwanda, the mean was 4.2000. Many respondents have confirmed that Current rate

methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure. Hedging Translation exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit as the mean is 4.1600 which means agree. Hedging Translation exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets as 94% of the respondents confirmed the statement. Even if there is not any homogeneity in answers of the participants, there is no problem we gave greater value to the means of the statements.

The basic data from the interview and other statistical analyses undertaken in addition to the ones mentioned above have also supported the aforementioned conclusions. In the discussion of the findings, the study also cited what other earlier researchers had discovered regarding the function of hedging Translation exposure for the management of foreign exchange risks.

4.3.3. Descriptive statistics on the hedging Operational exposure for foreign currency risks control in tea exporters companies.

The operational exposure for foreign currency risk control in tea exporters enterprises is discussed in several ways in the following table. The maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviations were given for each assertion. The table looks at the third goal, which is investigating how tea exporters might mitigate operational exposure to foreign exchange risks. (Strongly Disagree = 1, Disagree = 2, Neutral = 3, Agree = 4, and Strongly Agree = 5).

Apart from the results from the below table, the fundamental information from the interview as well as additional statistical analyses conducted in addition to those already discussed have confirmed the findings that were made above. The study also included findings from past studies highlighting the role of hedging Translation exposure for the management of foreign exchange risks in its discussion of the results.

TABLE 13: THE EFFECTS OF HEDGING OPERATIONAL EXPOSURE ON FOREIGN CURRENCY RISKS FOR TEA EXPORTERS

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.0800	.82906
The company uses Back-to-back loans techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.71027
The company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.79179
The company uses Cross-currency swap techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1200	.68928
The Company's budgets and forecasts minimizes the Foreign currency risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.61809
The economic exposure enhances the Company's competitive position in the market even if there are changes in exchange rate.	50	2.00	5.00	4.0600	.65184
The operating exposure doesn't affect negatively the Company's profitability	50	2.00	5.00	4.0000	.78246
Speculating on currency direction over a given period of time is a culture in our company	50	2.00	5.00	4.2400	.55549
Hedging operational exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit.	50	2.00	5.00	4.1600	.71027
Hedging operational exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets	50	1.00	5.00	4.1400	.85738
Valid N (listwise)	50				

Source: Primary data, author's computation using SPSS 22.0. September 8th, 2022

The findings from the table 13 indicated that the company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid foreign currency risks as it was indicated by the mean of 4.0800 which implies agree. Many respondents pointed out that the company uses Back-to-back loans techniques so as to avoid foreign currency risks. The company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid foreign currency risks, this was agreed by many of the study participants.

The study findings indicated that many of the study respondents agreed that the company uses Cross-currency swap techniques so as to avoid foreign currency risks. The Company's budgets and forecasts minimizes the foreign currency risks as it was pointed out by many respondents due to the mean of 4.1600 which mean agree. The economic exposure enhances the Company's competitive position in the market even if there are changes in exchange rate as many respondents agreed the statement.

The operating exposure doesn't affect negatively the Company' profitability as the mean is 4.0000 which means agree. The respondents from the selected five tea exporters in Rwanda affirmed Speculating on currency direction over a given period of time is a culture in their company. The findings indicated also that hedging operational exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit, this is due to the mean of 4.1600 which means agree. Hedging operational exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets as many of the participants confirmed the statement. Within all assertions, the value of the standard deviation is greater than 0.5 which refers to the absence of homogeneity. This is not a challenge as we appreciated the values of mean.

The above described statistics is all about statistics of the independent variables (hedging, Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks control and Hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks control and Hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks

control), it is necessary to conduct descriptive statistics about the dependent variable (The level of Foreign Currency risks control).

4.3.4. Descriptive statistics on the level of foreign currency risks control for tea exporters

The following table verifies the level of foreign currency risks control for tea exporters within the five selected tea exporters in Rwanda. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree. The maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviations were given for each assertion. This part provides more information on the dependent variable of the study (Foreign currency risks control). According to Table 14, there were 50 respondents who were the subject of the investigation. Regarding the importance of hedging transactions for managing foreign exchange risks in tea exporter enterprises, the minimum response is 2 and the maximum is 5, which denotes a strong agreement.

TABLE 14: THE LEVEL OF FOREIGN CURRENCY RISKS CONTROL FOR TEA EXPORTERS**Descriptive Statistics**

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is no transaction risks in the Company	50	2.00	5.00	4.0800	.82906
There is no translation risks in the Company	50	2.00	5.00	4.3400	.59281
There is no operational or economic risks in the Company	50	2.00	5.00	4.1400	.85738
The Company is paid very well when the buyers agreed to repay at an agreed rate on a specified later date	50	2.00	5.00	4.1400	.70015
In the Company selling for immediate settlement doesn't cause foreign exchange risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2800	.57286
In the Company hedging strategies helps to address financial and nonfinancial risks	50	2.00	5.00	4.2200	.64807
The company achieves its goals in terms of managing currency risk	50	2.00	5.00	4.1400	.78272
There is no income uncertainty in the Company due to foreign exchange exposure	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.63888
The profit of the company increases due to foreign currency risks control	50	2.00	5.00	4.2000	.63888
There is no new investments due to the foreign currency risks control in the company	50	2.00	5.00	4.1800	.62890
Valid N (listwise)	50				

Source: Primary data, author's computation using SPSS 22.0. September 8th, 2022

The findings from the table 14 indicated that there is no transaction risks in the Company as the mean is 4.0800 which means agree. There is no translation risks in the Company as it was agreed

by many of the study respondents. The participants confirmed that there is no operational or economic risks in the Company, this was indicated by the mean of 4.1400 which means agree. The Company is paid very well when the buyers agreed to repay at an agreed rate on a specified later date, this was approved by many of the study participants from the five selected Tea Exporters Companies in Rwanda.

In the Company selling for immediate settlement doesn't cause foreign exchange risks as it was affirmed by many of the study participants. Majority of the study respondents pointed out that in the Company hedging strategies helps to address financial and nonfinancial risks. The company achieves its goals in terms of managing currency risk as many participants confirmed the statement with the mean of 4.1400 which means agree.

There is no income uncertainty in the Company due to foreign exchange exposure. This was agreed by many of the study respondents from the selected five Tea Exporters Companies in Rwanda. The study participants confirmed that the profit of the company increases due to foreign currency risks control. This is indicated by the mean of 4.2000 which means agree. The participants confirmed that there is no new investments due to the foreign currency risks control in the company. For all the above statements the standard deviation is greater than 0.5 which implies heterogeneity, but absence of homogeneity was not a problem as the common observations of the respondents were indicated by the means.

4.4. Regression analysis

The regression analysis has been chosen as a reliable method of identifying which variables have impact on a topic of interest. The process of performing a regression allowed the researcher to confidently determine which factors matter most and how these factors influence each other. This

part involves pointing out the variables of the study, model summary, ANOVA, coefficients of the study analysis and hypothesis testing.

4.4.1. Variables of the study

The researcher indicated the main variables of the study before pointing out the relationship among variables. The following table indicates the study variables.

TABLE 15: VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Hedging operational exposure , Hedging translation exposure , Hedging transaction exposure ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Foreign Currency risks control

b. All requested variables entered.

Source: Elaborated by the Author using SPSS 22.0

The table 15 indicated that the independent variables are Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure^b and the dependent variable is Foreign currency risk control. The study pointed out the correlation of each independent variable to the dependent variable. The study indicated also the contribution of all the factors examined together on the dependent variable.

4.4.2. Model Summary

A model summary has been automatically created when running a regression modeling or a classification modeling. The model summary displays the name of the model, the model type, and the model formula. The following part describes the model summary of the study where the coefficient of determination (R Square) has been pointed out. This indicates the level at which independent variables (Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging

operational exposure) cause variation in dependent variable (Foreign currency risk control). The model summary is illustrated within the below part.

TABLE 16: MODEL SUMMARY

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.989 ^a	.978	.974	74.8971

a. Predictors: (Constant), Hedging operational exposure , Hedging translation exposure , Hedging transaction exposure

b. Dependent Variable: Foreign Currency risks control

Source: Elaborated by the Author using SPSS 22.0

The R-Squared was used to show the variation of the dependent variable that could be explained by the independent variables. The R-Squared is .978 implying that 97.8% of the foreign currency risk control in Tea Exporters Companies could be explained by independent independents variables (Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure).

4.4.3. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

TABLE 17: ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	138723012712347331111.000	3	7216711757112821111.000	125.230	.001 ^b
	Residual	7200573837007541200.000	46	2272988107631`63310.000		
	Total	25703459655556633333.000	49			

a. Dependent Variable: Foreign Currency Risks Control

b. Predictors: (Constant), Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure

Source: Computed by the author using SPSS 22.0, September, 2022

In determining whether the model was good fit for data, the study adopted the use of analysis of variance. The value of the F-Critical (8.14) was less than the F-calculated (125.230) and the P-

Value (0.001) was below the significant level, implying that the model could be used in predicting the contribution of Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure (Independent variables) on Foreign Currency Risks Control (Dependent variable) in Rwanda

4.4.4. Coefficients

TABLE 18: COEFFICIENTS

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	66.758	14.231		4.691	.000
	Hedging transaction exposure (X1)	10.265	1.093	-.119	-18.540	.000
	Hedging translation exposure (x2)	8.429	.200	1.068	42.211	.000
	Hedging operational exposure (X3)	2.885	.543	-.132	-5.312	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Foreign currency risk control (Y)

Source: Elaborated by the author using SPSS 22.0

From the data in table 18, the established regression equation was:

$$Y = 66.758 + 10.265X1 + 8.429X2 + 2.885X3$$

As presented in the above table, Hedging Transaction Exposure has a significant positive influence on Foreign Currency Risks Control as indicated by regression coefficient of 10.265 and P-value of 0.000. It is also clear that Hedging translation exposure has a significant positive influence on Foreign Currency Risks Control as indicated by regression coefficient of 8.429 and P-value of 0.000. Hedging operational exposure has a significant positive influence on Foreign Currency Risks as indicated by regression coefficient of 2.885 and P-value of 0.000. As matter of the fact, it is very true to confirm that all independent variables have an impact on economic growth in Rwanda.

4.4.5. The Relationship between Independent variables and the dependent variable of the study

The relationship between Independent variables and the dependent variable of the study is explained by the correlation matrix. The following table indicates the correlation coefficients for all the variables of the study. The matrix depicts the correlation between all the possible pairs of values in a table.

TABLE 19: CORRELATION MATRIX

		Foreign currency risk control	Hedging transaction exposure	Hedging translation exposure	Hedging operational exposure
Foreign currency risk control	Pearson Correlation	1	.982**	.816**	.951**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	50	50	50	50
Hedging transaction exposure	Pearson Correlation	.982**	1	-.353**	-.314**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	50	50	50	50
Hedging translation exposure	Pearson Correlation	.816**	-.353**	1	.671**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	50	50	50	50
Hedging operational exposure	Pearson Correlation	.951**	-.314**	.671**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	50	50	50	50

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Elaborated by the author using SPSS 22.0

The findings from the table 19 indicated that there is a positive relationship between Hedging transaction exposure and foreign currency risk control. This is indicated by a positive coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.982$) and the relationship is statistically significant as the Sig. (2-tailed) or P-value (.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The value of Pearson correlation lies between $0.7 < r < 0.9$ which implies High correlation. The findings allowed us to accept the first

hypothesis which states that hedging Transaction exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda.

The findings from the table 19 indicated that there is a positive relationship between Hedging translation exposure and foreign currency risk control. This is indicated by a positive coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.816$) and the relationship is statistically significant as the Sig. (2-tailed) or P-value (.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The value of Pearson correlation lies between $0.7 < r < 0.9$ which implies High correlation. The findings allowed us to accept the second hypothesis which states that hedging Translation exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda.

The findings from the table 19 indicated that there is a positive relationship between Hedging operational exposure and foreign currency risk control. This is indicated by a positive coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.951$) and the relationship is statistically significant as the Sig. (2-tailed) or P-value (.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The value of Pearson correlation lies between $0.7 < r < 0.9$ which implies High correlation. The findings allowed us to accept the third hypothesis which states that hedging operational exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda. From the correlation matrix, the researcher has been able to conduct also the multicollinearity test among the independent variables of the study.

4.4.5. Multicollinearity test

The researcher has conducted Multicollinearity test as multicollinearity can lead to skewed or misleading results when a researcher or analyst attempts to determine how well each independent variable can be used most effectively to predict or understand the dependent variable in a statistical model. The following paragraph describes the test of multicollinearity.

The results from the above table (Table 19) indicated that there is no multicollinearity among independent variables (Hedging transaction exposure, Hedging translation exposure and Hedging operational exposure) of the study. This is because, the Pearson correlation coefficients are less than 80% as it was said by (Gujarati, 2004). This is a good indicator that predictors are not highly linearly related. As matter of the fact, it very clear that the model is valid and correct.

4.4.6. Hypothesis testing

The following figure describes the linear patterns that helped in hypotheses verification. The first hypothesis states that “Hedging Transaction exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda”. The second hypothesis states that “Hedging Translation exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda”. The third hypothesis states that “Hedging Operating exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda”. The following figure indicates the set of linear graphs that helped in hypotheses testing.

Figure 2: Hypotheses testing

Source: Illustrated by the researcher using SPSS 22.0

4.4.6.1. First hypothesis: Hedging Transaction exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda

Provided that the Scatterplots with a linear pattern have points that seem to generally fall along a line. It is evident that there is an association between the variables (Hedging Transaction exposure and Foreign currency risks control). This implies a positive relationship between Hedging transaction exposure and Foreign currency risks control in Rwanda. For this reason, it is evident to accept the first hypothesis which states that hedging Transaction exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks

control for tea exporters in Rwanda. The verification of the first hypothesis implies the achievement of the first objective.

4.4.6.2. Second hypothesis: Hedging Translation exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda.

Provided that the Scatterplots with a linear pattern have points that seem to generally fall along a line. It is evident that there is an association between the variables (Hedging Translation exposure and Foreign currency risks control). This implies a positive relationship between Hedging translation exposure and Foreign currency risks control in Rwanda. For this reason, it is evident to accept the second hypothesis which states that hedging Translation exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda. The verification of the second hypothesis implies the achievement of the second objective.

4.4.6.3. Third hypothesis: Hedging Operating exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda”

Provided that the Scatterplots with a linear pattern have points that seem to generally fall along a line. It is evident that there is an association between the variables (Hedging operational exposure and Foreign currency risks control). This implies a positive relationship between Hedging operational exposure and Foreign currency risks control in Rwanda. For this reason, it is evident to accept the third hypothesis which states that hedging operational exposure has a significant effect on foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda. The verification of the third hypothesis implies the achievement of the third objective.

4.4.6. Normality test

A normality test is a process used to determine if a group of data fits a standard normal distribution. In statistics, normality tests are used to determine if a data set is well-modelled by a normal

distribution and to compute how likely it is for a variable underlying the data set to be normally distributed. The normality means that the distribution of the test is normally distributed with 0 mean, with 1 standard deviation a symmetric bell-shaped curve.

H_0 : The residuals are normally distributed

H_1 : The residuals are not normally distributed

To perform this test of normality the histogram system and Normal P-P Plot by using SPSS 22.0, we found the following results:

Source: Elaborated by the author using SPSS 22.0

The figure in the Bell-shaped indicated that residuals are normally distributed. This allowed the researcher to accept the Null hypothesis (H_0) that the residuals are normally distributed. This

implies the accuracy, validity and correctness of the model. The normal distribution has been also tested using Normal P-P Plot. The following figure indicates the test of normal distribution using Normal P-P Plot.

FIGURE 4: NORMAL P-P PLOT

Source: Elaborated by the author using SPSS 22.0.

According to the above figure, Normal P-P Plot indicated that residuals are normal distributed as well as the dots fall on the line. This implies the validity, accuracy and correctness of the model. In this way, the alternative hypothesis that the residuals are not normally distributed is rejected

and the null hypothesis that the residuals are normally distributed is accepted. The researcher concluded that, the model is good to be used.

4.4.7. Heteroskedasticity test

The heteroskedasticity test which is also called White test is a statistical test that establishes whether residual variance of variables in regression model is constant. And it is said to occur when the variance of the unobservable error condition on independent variables, is not constant.

Ho: No heteroskedasticity (presence of homoskedasticity)

H1: Existence of heteroskedasticity (absence of homoscedasticity)

FIGURE 5: HETEROSKEDASTICITY TEST

Source: Elaborated by the author using SPSS 22.0

The above results showed that, there is no systematic pattern, means that the plot is randomly scattered. This implies that the null hypothesis must be accepted and the alternative one must be rejected. Then, the researcher concluded that, errors of unobserved independent variables present a quality of Homoskedasticity. As well as there is no heteroskedastic effect, the model is correct and valid and must be accepted.

4.5. Discussion on the results from interview

During interview the general managers in Tea Exporters Companies pointed out that there is a policy of hedging foreign exchange exposure in minimizing the foreign currency risk in their Companies. Even if it is a policy they have pointed out some internal challenges that they face while hedging foreign exchange exposure in controlling the foreign currency risk such as Take Treasury's hedge strategies and document them for special hedge accounting when applicable, Account and report on all of the Company's derivatives both designated and non-designated with limited resources and often limited experience in this most difficult accounting area, ineffective foreign exposure hedging experts and Communicate effectively with management.

The interviewed managers in the five selected tea exporters companies pointed out that there some threats they face while hedging foreign exchange exposure in controlling the foreign currency risk such as exchange rate movements and the government monetary policy which is characterized by increase in money supply. The interviewed pointed out that there some negative effects of exchange rate movements on profit margins in their company. The interviewed revealed also that hedging foreign exchange exposure in their organizations have some negative impacts including the reduction in risk provided by hedging also typically results in a reduction in potential profits. Hedging requires one to pay money for the protection it provides, known as the premium.

The results from interview allowed the researcher to confirm the reliability of a research instrument as the instrument yields the same results. This is because the results from interviewed director managers are the same to the results obtained from the staff investigated through questionnaires.

CHAPTER 5: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. Introduction

This section involves summary of the findings, conclusion drawn from the findings and recommendations for policy and practice. Both the conclusions and recommendations were made as per the general and specific objectives of the study. The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of hedging foreign currency exposure on foreign currency risk control in Rwanda. st

5.2. Summary of the Findings

This section presents the summary of the findings on the influence of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda, hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda and hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda.

5.2.1. The role of hedging Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda

The study found that hedging Transaction exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks for tea exporters ($\beta=0.982$, P-value = 0.000). The overall mean for all the statement is 4.2060 which means Agree. The respondents gave their consent for the company to employ forward contracts procedures to manage foreign exchange risks. Techniques for futures contracts are also employed to reduce foreign exchange concerns. The business uses money market hedge strategies to reduce foreign exchange risks. The business uses currency option hedge strategies to reduce foreign exchange risks.

Respondents from the five tea exporting enterprises in Rwanda who were chosen also confirmed that the company effectively uses risk shifting tactics to reduce foreign exchange risks. The business effectively employs currency risk-sharing strategies to reduce foreign exchange hazards. Participants in the survey concur that the business employs leading and lagging strategies to lower foreign exchange risks.

According to all research participants' replies, the corporation used rein voicing centers approaches to manage its foreign exchange risks. Many respondents concur that there is no cost associated with hedging Transaction exposure that tends to reduce profit. As the study's participants confirmed, hedging transaction exposure does not need investing in the systems required to facilitate trading that could cause the organization to fail its goals. In actuality, it is true to say that hedging Transaction exposure contributes significantly to the foreign exchange risks control faced by Rwandan tea exporters.

5.2.2. The impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda

The study found that hedging Translation exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks for tea exporters ($\beta=0.816$, P-value = 0.000). The overall mean for all the statement is 4.1580 which means Agree. According to the findings, the corporation used purchasing currency swap procedures to manage foreign exchange risks. The large majority of responders who agreed with the statement suggested as much. The corporation acquires foreign currency to be placed on the foreign currency account in order to be able to pay international expenses at a cheaper cost. The respondents confirmed that the company uses futures contracts to hedge its exposure to foreign exchange risks.

Participants in the study concur that gains on forward contracts used to hedge translation exposure that are taxed in their enterprises as tea exporters pose no problem. Effective management of translation exposure can be achieved using both modern and antiquated techniques. Effective management of translation exposure is achieved via the use of both monetary and non-monetary means.

The foregoing hedging strategies can be combined to effectively reduce translation exposure. Numerous responders have attested to the effectiveness of current rate strategies in managing translation exposure. There is no cost associated with hedging translation exposure, which usually results in higher profits. It is not necessary to invest in the systems required to support trade that can cause a corporation to miss goals while hedging translation exposure. As a result, it is accurate to state that hedging Translation exposure contributes significantly to foreign exchange risks control for Rwandan tea exporters.

5.2.3. The effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters in Rwanda

The study found that hedging operational exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks control for tea exporters ($\beta=0.951$, P-value = 0.000). The overall mean for all the statement is 4.1580 which means Agree. The results of the table showed that the corporation uses debt financing strategies to reduce foreign exchange risks. Many responses emphasized the usage of back-to-back borrowing procedures by the business to reduce foreign exchange risks. Participants in the research agreed that the company uses debt financing strategies to reduce foreign exchange risks.

According to the study's findings, the respondents agreed that the company uses cross-currency swap procedures to minimize foreign exchange risks. As several respondents noted, the company's budgeting and forecasts reduce the risks associated with foreign currencies. According to several respondents, the economic exposure improves the company's competitive position in the market even if the exchange rate changes.

The company's profitability is unaffected negatively by the operating exposure. Respondents from the five Rwandan tea exporters that were chosen confirmed that it is a culture in their business to speculate on currency direction over a specific time period. The results also showed that there is no cost associated with hedging operational exposure that tends to reduce earnings. As the participants agreed, hedging operational exposure does not need investing in the systems required to support trading that could cause the company to fail its goals. In actuality, it is true to say that hedging operational exposure contributes significantly to the management of foreign exchange risks for Rwandan tea exporters.

5.3. Conclusion

The study concludes that hedging Transaction exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda. This transaction exposure hedging involved Forward contracts techniques, Futures contracts techniques, Money market hedge techniques, Currency option hedge techniques, risk shifting techniques, currency risk sharing techniques, leading and lagging techniques and re-invoicing centers techniques.

The study concludes that hedging Translation exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda. This translation exposure hedging involved Purchasing currency swaps, purchases foreign currency to be put on the foreign currency account, futures

contracts techniques, Current and non-current methods, Monetary and Non-monetary methods, Current rate methods and a combination of the previous listed hedging techniques.

The study concludes that hedging operational exposure significantly affects foreign currency risks control for tea exporters in Rwanda. This operational exposure hedging involved Debt financing techniques, Back-to-back loans techniques, Debt financing techniques, Cross-currency swap techniques and Company's budgets and forecasts.

5.4. Suggestions

The study found that hedging transaction exposure has a significant influence on foreign currency risks control. Therefore, the study recommends that the general managers should compare the cash flows that could be expected from each hedging technique before determining which technique to apply.

The study found that hedging translation exposure has a significant influence on foreign currency risks control. Therefore, the study recommends that the general managers should avoid inaccurate earnings forecasts, inadequate forward contracts for some currencies and avoid accounting distractions.

The study found that hedging operational exposure has a significant influence on foreign currency risks control. Therefore, the study recommends that the general managers should promote diversification of production facilities, try to balance insurance against profit as some hedging strategies reduce profits.

The Governments of Rwanda should stabilize its exchange rates by importing a smaller amount of goods and promoting the export a larger amount. Similarly, they can devalue other currencies to boost the status of their own by selling them to other countries.

5.5. Areas for further research

Since this research project focused on the analysis of the influence of hedging foreign currency exposure in foreign currency risks control, we only examined the issues related to the subject matter of study. Then we encourage the future researchers to make research on other determinants of foreign currency risks control. Researchers may also conduct a study on the factors that hinder hedging foreign currency exposure.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE RESERVED TO THE STAFF IN FINANCIAL DEPARTMENT IN FIVE TOP TEA EXPORTERS IN RWANDA

Instructions

1. The questionnaire is divided two: Personal identification of participants and Specific objectives questions
2. Tick the answer that you think is the most right to each question by Putting the sign”✓“in the appropriate reserved space
3. Feel open because the information you provide will be kept secretary

A. Personal identification

a) Gender

Male

Female

b) Age

21- 30 years

31- 40 years

41- 50 years

51 and above

c) Marital status

Single

Married

Divorced

Widower

d) Educational level

- Advanced level (A2)
- Diploma (A1)
- Bachelors' degree (A0)
- Masters' degree
- Graduate with a professional course

e) How long have you been working in your Company?

- 1 - 3 years
- 4- 6 years
- 7 years and above

f) Tea Exporter Company

- Rwanda Mountain Tea
- SORWATHE Tea
- Karongi Tea Factory Limited
- Rwanda Tea
- Gisovu Tea Estate

B. General information (as per research objectives)

Objective one: Questions that verify the first objective of exploring the role of hedging

Transaction exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2=

Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree

	Items	1	2	3	4	5
1	The company uses Forward contracts techniques in order to control foreign currency risks					
2	The company uses Futures contracts techniques in order to minimize foreign currency risks					
3	The company uses Money market hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks					
4	The company uses Currency option hedge techniques in order to avoid foreign currency risks					
5	The company uses risk shifting techniques effectively in order to minimize foreign currency risks					
6	The company uses currency risk sharing techniques effectively in order to avoid foreign currency risks					
7	The company uses leading and lagging techniques in order to reduce foreign currency risks					
8	The company uses rein voicing centers techniques in order to manage foreign currency risks					
9	Hedging Transaction exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit.					
10	Hedging Transaction exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets					

Objective two: Questions that verify the second objective of analyzing the impact of hedging Translation exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	Items	1	2	3	4	5
1	The company uses Purchasing currency swaps techniques in order to control foreign currency risks					
2	The company purchases foreign currency to be put on the foreign currency account so as to be able to meet outside country expenses at lower cost					
3	The Company uses Hedging through futures contracts techniques so as to control foreign currency risks					
4	There is no challenge due to gains on forward contracts used to hedge translation exposure that are taxed					
5	Current and non-current methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure					
6	Monetary and Non-monetary methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure					
7	Using a combination of the above hedging techniques is an effective way of controlling translation exposure					
8	Current rate methods are used effectively in order to manager translation exposure					
9	Hedging Translation exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit.					
10	Hedging Translation exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets					

Objective three: Questions that verify the third objective of determining the effects of hedging operational exposure on foreign currency risks for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	Items	1	2	3	4	5
1	The company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks					
2	The company uses Back-to-back loans techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks					
3	The company uses Debt financing techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks					
4	The company uses Cross-currency swap techniques so as to avoid Foreign currency risks					
5	The Company's budgets and forecasts minimizes the Foreign currency risks					
6	The economic exposure enhances the Company's competitive position in the market even if there are changes in exchange rate.					
7	The operating exposure doesn't affect negatively the Company' profitability					
8	Speculating on currency direction over a given period of time is a culture in our company					
9	Hedging operational exposure does not involve a cost that tends to lower the profit.					
10	Hedging operational exposure does not require investment in the processes needed to support trading that can lead the company to miss targets					

The level of foreign currency risks control for tea exporters. Questions that verify the level of foreign currency risks control for tea exporters. (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

	Items	1	2	3	4	5
1	There is no transaction risks in the Company					
2	There is no translation risks in the Company					
3	There is no operational or economic risks in the Company					
4	The Company is paid very well when the buyers agreed to repay at an agreed rate on a specified later date.					
5	In the Company selling for immediate settlement doesn't cause foreign exchange risks					
6	In the Company hedging strategies helps to address financial and nonfinancial risks					
7	The company achieves its goals in terms of managing currency risk					
8	There is no income uncertainty in the Company due to foreign exchange exposure.					
9	The profit of the company increases due to foreign currency risks control					
10	There is no new investments due to the foreign currency risks control in the company					

Thanks for your cooperation

APPENDIX 2: INTERVIEW RESERVED TO THE GENERAL MANAGERS IN THE TOP FIVE TEA EXPORTERS IN RWANDA

Interview will be conducted with the 5 General Managers in the selected top five tea exporters in Rwanda.

1. What is your policy about hedging foreign exchange exposure in minimizing the foreign currency risk?
2. Which internal challenges do you face while hedging foreign exchange exposure in controlling the foreign currency risk?
3. Which threats do you face while hedging foreign exchange exposure in controlling the foreign currency risk?
4. How are you seeing the effects of exchange rate movements on profit margins in you company?
5. a) Is there any impact of foreign exchange exposure in your organization?
b) If yes, explain

Thanks for your cooperation